

need to be continuously flooded throughout the cropping period; a rice crop can be safely irrigated at -10 kPa matric suction without causing any

decline in rice yield. This suction, as observed in some field experiments, arrives in about 3-4 d in medium-textured soils in subtropical climates.

The procedure saved about 16% of the water used to keep soil continuously submerged under 30 mm of water. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Mass screening and identification of rice germplasm tolerant of light and temperature stress

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Rice adaptation to light and temperature stresses is the basis of stable yield. Few simple and easy techniques exist to test rice germplasm for tolerance for these stresses.

We screened rice germplasm for shading tolerance using the method of Murty (1992). We divided the identified varieties into two groups during elongation stage. One group was placed in natural light, the other in the shade (1/5 natural light). After 14 d, the dry weight of the two groups was measured at the booting stage. The ratio of dry weight under shading to that under natural light was used as the shading tolerance index.

At the same time, germplasm was screened for tolerance for photooxidation using the method of Jiao (1992). Mature rice leaves were detached at heading stage and submerged in a white tray filled with water containing 5 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2$ and 350 $\mu\text{mol O}_2$ under sunlight at 30-35 °C for 5-7 d. A transparent glass bar covered the leaves to prevent floating. Photooxidation-tolerant varieties whose chlorophyll contents were 3.0-4.78 mg dm^{-2} were graded 1-2, whereas sensitive varieties whose chlorophyll contents were 0.8-2.2 mg dm^{-2} were graded 4-5 (see table).

From 1993 to 1995, we identified 41 rice germplasm accessions using this technique. Results indicated four photosynthetic ecological types

Photooxidation and shading tolerance in different rice varieties.

Variety	Dry weight plant ⁻¹ (g)		S/N×100%	Photooxidative treatment	
	Natural light (N)	Shading (S)		Chl content (mg dm^{-2})	Grade ^a
1995					
Yue A (I)	5.37 ± 0.12	2.51 ± 0.12	46.72	1.45 ± 0.10	5
Yue A/R3049 (I)	5.15 ± 0.14	3.48 ± 0.17	67.57	1.66 ± 0.11	4
R3049 (I)	5.19 ± 0.15	1.78 ± 0.12	34.24	2.10 ± 0.21	4
Yue A/R3043 (I)	3.26 ± 0.15	2.68 ± 0.13	82.17	2.53 ± 0.17	3
R3043 (I)	4.33 ± 0.65	2.31 ± 0.15	53.31	3.36 ± 0.19	2
Yue A/R3034 (I)	4.38 ± 0.53	3.17 ± 0.21	72.44	1.77 ± 0.23	4
R3034 (I)	5.14 ± 0.21	2.16 ± 0.21	41.95	2.84 ± 0.29	3
Yue A/R3035 (I)	6.32 ± 0.25	3.33 ± 0.31	52.58	0.81 ± 0.09	5
R3035 (I)	4.90 ± 0.13	1.64 ± 0.11	33.54	1.22 ± 0.10	5
Yue A/R3044 (I)	5.75 ± 0.11	3.63 ± 0.29	62.91	2.49 ± 0.14	3
R3044 (I)	8.56 ± 0.25	3.29 ± 0.25	38.45	0.84 ± 0.08	5
Yue A/R437 (J)	6.35 ± 0.35	1.94 ± 0.15	30.59	1.45 ± 0.09	5
R437 (J)	6.06 ± 0.15	2.32 ± 0.19	38.32	2.24 ± 0.17	4
Yue A/J204 (J)	3.85 ± 0.20	2.46 ± 0.13	64.51	2.45 ± 0.10	3
J204 (J)	5.56 ± 0.12	1.61 ± 0.10	28.92	2.21 ± 0.13	4
Yue A/320500 (J)	6.88 ± 0.20	2.40 ± 0.12	34.94	1.99 ± 0.12	4
320500 (J)	5.58 ± 0.30	3.03 ± 0.31	54.30	1.28 ± 0.13	5
Yue A/30152 (I)	3.80 ± 0.17	1.94 ± 0.17	51.05	1.49 ± 0.10	5
Yue A/34077 (I)	4.65 ± 0.27	1.92 ± 0.15	41.29	2.58 ± 0.15	3
34077 (I)	4.42 ± 0.29	2.81 ± 0.21	63.50	3.14 ± 0.27	2
Yue A/42525 (I)	6.29 ± 0.21	2.75 ± 0.19	43.80	2.09 ± 0.19	4
1994					
Liuqianxin S/JW201 (J)	14.60 ± 1.68	6.90 ± 0.49	47.30	3.50 ± 0.25	3
Liuqianxin S (J)	15.50 ± 2.15	7.90 ± 0.58	51.00	3.31 ± 0.30	3
JW201 (J)	13.70 ± 1.89	8.80 ± 0.70	64.20	3.03 ± 0.25	3
JW207 (I)	12.10 ± 1.93	6.00 ± 0.57	49.60	2.21 ± 0.18	4
Liuqianxin S/JW207 (J)	13.90 ± 2.11	7.40 ± 0.49	53.20	2.33 ± 0.10	3
276 (J)	14.40 ± 2.99	6.50 ± 0.35	45.10	3.28 ± 0.27	4
Liuqianxin S/276 (J)	18.00 ± 2.29	10.50 ± 1.51	58.30	1.48 ± 0.09	5
Pelai 64S (I)	16.20 ± 2.44	6.20 ± 0.53	38.30	1.91 ± 0.11	4
1993					
02428 (J)	8.70 ± 0.53	5.90 ± 0.52	67.80	4.78 ± 0.35	1
Yayou 2 (J) B	10.50 ± 1.41	6.60 ± 0.39	62.90	3.93 ± 0.59	2
HX-3 (I)	28.01 ± 3.68	16.15 ± 3.10	57.66	2.56 ± 0.19	3
Minghui 63 (I)	16.05 ± 2.97	5.56 ± 0.29	34.61	2.27 ± 0.21	3
Shanyou 63 (I) D	11.50 ± 1.87	7.90 ± 0.48	68.70	1.73 ± 0.17	4
Jin gang 30 (I)	8.50 ± 0.36	4.30 ± 0.31	50.60	1.03 ± 0.16	5
Xiangxian (I) F	11.40 ± 2.16	3.10 ± 0.30	27.20	1.20 ± 0.11	5
Tsukushibare (J) C	7.00 ± 0.36	2.10 ± 0.21	30.30	3.03 ± 0.31	2
Corn-rice (I)	4.60 ± 0.38	3.30 ± 0.21	71.70	1.36 ± 0.10	5
Nanjing 14 (I) E	8.70 ± 0.47	2.90 ± 0.19	33.30	2.75 ± 0.17	3
Wuyugeng (J) A	7.00 ± 0.41	4.10 ± 0.35	58.60	3.78 ± 0.43	2
Peiai 64S/JW201 (J)	16.10 ± 2.74	6.20 ± 0.58	38.50	1.40 ± 0.10	5

^aGrades (scores): 1 = green; 2 = tip is yellowish; 3 = 1/3 is yellowish; 4 = 1/2 is yellowish; 5 = whole leaf is yellowish. Shading period was from elongation to booting. Photooxidative treatment was conducted at booting stage for 6 d.

adapted to light intensity. One was adapted to a wide range of light intensities, including japonica rice 02428, Wuyugeng, and indica-japonica

hybrid rice YueA/ R 3043, Yayou 2. During the heading stage, photosynthetic rate at high (40 °C) and low temperatures (15 °C) was determined

Differences in photosynthetic rates of six rice varieties under low (15 °C). A = Wuyugeng, B = Yayou 2, C = Tsukushibare, D = Shanhou 63, E = Nanjing 14, F = Xiangxian.

using a Clark O₂ electrode and compared with the photosynthetic rate at optimum temperatures of 30-35 °C. The

ratio of photosynthesis under high and low temperature to that of optimum temperature was represented as a high- or low-temperature tolerance index. Six varieties were selected for their tolerance for temperature stress (see figure). The results showed that japonica rice Wuyugeng and indica-japonica hybrid Yayou 2 were tolerant of both high and low temperatures. Their photosynthetic rates were stable. Under field conditions, japonica rice Wuyugeng is tolerant of light and temperature stresses and its yield has been relatively stable at more than 9 t ha⁻¹.

Wuyugeng is now one of the main rice varieties in Jiangsu Province, China. On the contrary, indica rice Xiangxian, which is sensitive to light and temperature stresses, has not been grown in Jiangsu.

In general, the types adapted to wide ranges of light and temperature were mostly japonica and indica-japonica rice varieties. In the region near the middle or lower reaches of the Yangtze River, selecting japonica rice and indica-japonica hybrid rice varieties adapted to wide ranges of light and temperature stresses may be an approach for rice breeders to use for obtaining high and stable yield. ■

Stress tolerance — adverse soils

Variation in salt tolerance among rice mutants and varieties based on yield attributes

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Around 100,000 of the 160,000 ha determined to be suitable for rice production in Cuba are affected by salt. We have therefore focused our rice breeding program on obtaining salt-tolerant genotypes.

We evaluated 9 mutants obtained from the J-112 variety through gamma radiation and 19 varieties for salt-tolerance field studies. The genotypes were studied in specially designed 3- × 3- × 1-m test plots in saline soil (plastic dark Gley Typic, with pH 7.44, 2000 ppm of total soluble solids, 0.90% organic matter, 0.003% N, 5.51 mg P100 g⁻¹ soil, and 11.68% mg K 100 g⁻¹ soil), and in nonstressed productive soil over two seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The crops were managed following local practices. Data on agronomic attributes (panicle length, panicle weight, filled grains

Clustering pattern among 28 rice genotypes and cluster means based on the saline stress tolerance indexes for different characters.

Cluster	Strains in each cluster	Saline stress tolerance index (%) based on				
		Panicle length	Panicle weight	Filled grains panicle ⁻¹	1000-grain weight	Grain yield
A	Theoretical check	100	100	100	100	100
B	RM12, RM62, RM41, RM66, RM114, RM157, RM72, RM120, RM153	92	90	90	88	50
C	IACUBA-26, Caribe I, IR5931, IR42, J112, 4024, 2006, CP3-C2, J104	88	80	85	83	45
D	Amistad-82, 6140	70	52	80	77	39
E	2005, 4014, IR8, 4032, 4034, MI-48, Perla	62	45	72	70	34

panicle⁻¹, 1000-grain weight, and grain yield) were collected from 10 randomly selected plants in each replication.

For all dates collected in the experiment, the saline stress tolerance index was calculated. To study the genotypic variation in the above characters, the data were processed further by using cluster analysis through Euclidian distance, including a theoretical check (100%) for all saline stress tolerance indexes.

In general, salinity markedly reduced agronomic attributes in all genotypes. Based on the Euclidian distance values, the population of 28 genotypes was grouped in 4 clusters (B, C, D, E) (see figure), indicating a great

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.